

**CONSERVATION OF PRIORITY
SPECIES OF MARINE
MEGAFUNA
IN GREECE AND ITALY**

D4.1: Replicability and Transferability Plan
(RTP)

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LIFE22-NAT-EL-LIFE MareNatura

“Conservation of priority species of marine megafauna in Greece and Italy”

Grant Agreement Project 101113792 - LIFE22-NAT-EL-LIFE MareNatura - LIFE-2022-SAP-NAT

Deliverable no and title:	D4.1: Replicability and Transferability Plan (RTP)
Delivery date:	M6 (31 December 2023)
Work package/Task:	WP4 Sustainability, replication and exploitation of project results / T4.1 Development of a Replicability and Transferability Plan
Task Leader:	Dimitra Petza (NECCA)
Partners involved:	NECCA, HCMR, ISPRA, NCC, UoC, MEDASSET
Author(s):	Zoi Mylona (NECCA), Elina Perrou (NECCA), Efterpi Patetsini (NECCA) Maria Trivourea (NECCA), Dimitra Petza (NECCA), Konstantina Andreanidou (MEDASSET), Kalliopi Baxevani (UoC), Dimitra Christidi (HOS), Georgia Alexopoulou (HOS), Panos Dendrinis (Mom), Maria Papazekou (UoA), Camilla Gotti (ISPRA)
Reviewer(s):	Michalis Probonas (UoC), Panagiotis Kasapidis (HCMR)
Submission date:	31 January 2024

Dissemination Level:		
PU	Public — fully open	X
SEN	Sensitive — limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement	

Change Records

Version	Date	Changes
1.0	31 Jan. 2024	

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Abbreviations

ABNJ	Areas Beyond National Jurisdiction
DST	Decision-Support Tool
EEZ	Exclusive Economic Zone
ESAS	European Seabirds At Sea
EU	European Union
HCMR	Hellenic Center for Marine Research
HOS	Hellenic Ornithological Society
IMP	Integrated Monitoring Plan
IMS	Integrated Monitoring System
ISPRA	Italian Institute for Environmental Protection and Research
MCS	Marine Conservation School
MCTF	Marine Conservation Task Force
MEDASSET	Mediterranean Association to Save the Sea Turtles
MMO	Marine Mammal Observation
MOBI	Mediterranean Offshore Biodiversity hotspots Inventory
MSP	Maritime Spatial Planning
N2K	Natura 2000
NECCA	Natural Environment and Climate Change Agency
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
NOA	National Observatory of Athens
PAMU	Protected Areas Management Unit
RTP	Replicability and Transferability Plan
SAC	Special Areas of Conservation
SCI	Sites of Community Importance
SCP	Systematic Conservation Planning
SPA	Special Protection Areas
SSCO	Site-Specific Conservation Objectives
T	Task
UNCLOS	United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea
UoA	University of the Aegean
UoC	University of Crete
WP	Work Package

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Summary

A Replicability and Transferability Plan is crucial for enhancing the project's impact by ensuring its lasting presence, scalability, expandability, and efficient use of resources. It also fosters the exchange of knowledge, mitigates risks and enhance a culture of continual learning and innovation both within the project and across its broader community. The Replicability and Transferability Plan (RTP) of the project LIFE MareNatura specifically aims to ensure that the outputs and the methods implemented will be able to be reproduced by interested parties of the project or other countries of the Eastern Mediterranean and the Black Sea.

The methodology followed consisted of six (6) key steps: 1) Define RTP objectives; 2) Select project actions for Replication and Transfer; 3) Define spatial implementation of the RTP; 4) Identify stakeholders; 5) Specify RTP Tools and define time planning; and 6) Propose funding / financial sources.

RTP objectives: The current RTP aims to i) increase the project's visibility, ii) highlight the effectiveness of created, tested and evaluated tools worthy for replication and transfer, and iii) act as a mean for broad acceptance and adoption by agencies, public structures, organizations and bodies involved in marine megafauna conservation.

Project actions for Replication and Transfer: Four (4) project actions were selected for replication and transfer: 1) The multidimensional approach for the monitoring of the target species; 2) The Decision Support Tool (DST) for Systematic Conservation Planning (SCP); 3) The Marine Conservation Task Force (MCTF); and 4) The identification of the Mediterranean Offshore Biodiversity hotspots Inventory (MOBI) of the target species.

Spatial implementation of the RTP: The Eastern Mediterranean and the Black Sea countries were considered for the spatial implementation of the RTP.

Stakeholders: The RTP was designed to cater to a broad range of target groups, including, among others, tourism professionals, professional and recreational fishers' associations, diving centres and associations, the general public, all users and interested parties in the marine realm, as well as stakeholders, including ministries and agencies, chambers, universities and research institutions, authorities responsible for Natura

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2000 (N2K) sites management, authorities regulating fishing activities, authorities responsible for energy and renewables, as well as NGOs involved in marine conservation.

RTP Tools and time planning: Thematic workshops, training sessions, communication and dissemination activities, public awareness and communication campaigns are the tools proposed by the RTP to enable replicability and transferability of relevant actions. The RTP's time planning aligns with the project deliverables and Work Packages' tasks duration.

Funding / financial sources: Various financial resources for replication are proposed encompassing National Funds, European Structural Funds for EU member states or horizontal European Funds, bilateral or multilateral State Agreements, private foundations, international organizations or NGOs.

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Chapter 1. Introduction

A Replicability and Transferability Plan (RTP) enhances a project's impact by ensuring its sustainability, scalability, and efficient use of resources. It also facilitates knowledge sharing, mitigates risks, and enhances a culture of learning and innovation within the project and its wider community.

The LIFE MareNatura Project foresees the development of a Replicability and Transferability Plan (RTP) that will ensure the extension of the Integrated Monitoring Plan (IMP) to other EU and non-EU countries of the Eastern Mediterranean and the Black Sea. It also anticipates the transferability and continuity of the project's results and outputs, through the mobilization of other regional networks and lobbying for the integration of biodiversity hotspots into the Natura 2000 (N2K) network, in collaboration with regional and international actors, and the establishment of MARBIONET, a Mediterranean Network of Marine Biodiversity Academics and NGOs. Drafting this Plan is essential to optimize the impact and reach of the project's methods and strategies. It highlights the value of proposed dissemination actions that were outlined in project's proposal, incorporating more tools to engage additional interested parties and partners.

The LIFE MareNatura project's RTP is structured in 3 Chapters:

Chapter 1 provides a general reference to the LIFE MareNatura RTP and a description of the RTP structure, with a brief presentation of the content of each RTP Chapter.

Chapter 2 gives an overview of the LIFE MareNatura Project. It contains information about the project's aim and objectives, the area of implementation, the target species, the means of achievement (i.e. Work Packages and Tasks), Deliverables and Expected Outcomes and briefly presents the Project's Consortium.

Chapter 3 is the core chapter of the RTP Plan. It explains what an RTP is and why it is useful to develop such a plan in the context of a LIFE project. It incorporates the methodology followed and it thoroughly describes the RTP's objectives and the project actions selected for replication and transfer. It also identifies the relevant stakeholders, specifies the tools to enable replicability and transferability actions,

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defines the timeframe of the Plan and provides information on the potential funding sources for the implementation of relevant replicability and transferability actions.

Finally, in **Appendix I** the list of relevant stakeholders is made available in an alphabetical order.

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Chapter 2. The LIFE MareNatura Project

2.1 Project Summary

The Mediterranean Sea is an area of conflicts and intensive human activities for millennia. It is also a Sea of Nature, a global biodiversity hotspot, facing immense conservation challenges. The LIFE MareNatura Project aims to provide the means for the mitigation of threats for nine (9) of the most threatened EU priority species including seabirds, marine turtles and marine mammals at the Ionian, South Adriatic and Aegean Seas, hosting the strongholds of target species populations in the 44 N2K project sites.

The project involves a wide consortium of experienced beneficiaries that are joining forces to sustain and effectively conserve the target species and their marine habitats. The consortium aims to cover existing knowledge gaps, by using a unique survey effort, along with modern technologies and methods for producing sufficient ecological information and appropriate planning tools, to:

- a. deal with the **conservation challenges of target species** in project area;
- b. create a **Mediterranean Offshore Biodiversity hotspots Inventory (MOBI)**;
- c. propose suitable **hotspots for inclusion in N2K network of Greece**;
- d. propose **Site Specific Conservation Objectives (SSCO) and Management Guidelines** for these new sites, as well as for the 44 project sites, ecologically linked with these hotspots (e.g. breeding sites of the target species);
- e. further improve the **conservation status of the MOBI sites located in Areas Beyond National Jurisdiction (ABNJ)**, by mobilizing stakeholders and policy groups;
- f. develop and implement an **Integrated Monitoring Scheme (IMS)** to regularly assess the species' conservation status;
- g. establish a **well-trained Marine Conservation Task Force (MCTF)** to apply conservation measures; and
- h. build the **capacity of competent authorities** for the conservation and active management of the project sites and the sustainability of the approach.

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The project runs by a large consortium consisting of twelve (12) partners under the coordination of the Hellenic Center for Marine Research (HCMR).

The project's duration is six (6) years, from July 2023 until June 2029.

The project's total budget is €10,707,187.54, while the EU's co-financing is €8,030,390.67 (i.e. 75.00% of total eligible costs).

2.2 Aim and Objectives

The project aims to efficiently protect nine (9) priority species of the Mediterranean marine megafauna.

The specific project objectives are the following:

- Carry out **ecological surveys for the project areas** (48M ha of marine area, which corresponds to more than 20% of the Mediterranean basin) with adequate experimental design, covering 188,000 km of aerial survey transects, and 10,000 nautical miles (10,000 nm) of boat survey transects, to obtain meaningful scientific data that will be used for the identification of hotspots for the conservation of the project's target species.
- Use the data produced for identifying the **Mediterranean Offshore Biodiversity hotspots Inventory (MOBI)**, including more than 30 sites in the Eastern Mediterranean, increasing the hotspot coverage in territorial waters by 10-15%, and including 20-30% of the Greek EEZ in MOBI and 10-20% of the waters in Areas Beyond National Jurisdiction (ABNJ), refining and updating the available data for existing or proposed biodiversity sites, as the most important, priority areas for conservation.
- **Provide concrete evidence and planning mechanisms for enlarging the Marine Protected Areas network in Greece**, to achieve the 30% EU's Biodiversity Strategy 2030 objective by proposing adequate marine biodiversity hotspots (more than 10 new SPAs and more than 10 new SACs) in the Greek territorial waters and the Greek EEZ to be designated as N2K sites, implementing a SCP and monitoring approach.
- **Promote the conservation of the rest of the MOBI hotspots, located in Areas Beyond National Jurisdiction** in international conventions and agreements, through devoted advocacy.
- Provide **adequate data to IUCN and Birdlife International for**

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further updating the IBAs, KBAs and IMMAs databases with valuable information on the target species and their habitats in offshore and onshore waters of the project area.

- Improve the management of the marine protected areas by **setting/updating the conservation objectives of each Greek project site (41 sites in total), as well as by proposing Site Specific Conservation Objectives (SSCOs) and Management Guidelines** for the new candidate marine N2K sites (at least 20 sites) and all the MOBI sites (at least 30 sites).
- Improve the decision-making process regarding nature conservation strategies, spatial planning and threat mitigation in Greece, Italy and Cyprus, by developing a **transparent and flexible Decision-Support Tool (DST)** for SCP and demonstrating an ecosystem-based approach to spatial planning in the marine environment.
- Establish and pilot implement an **Integrated Monitoring Scheme** of project sites and MOBI sites, for the regular assessment of the conservation status of the target species and their habitats, by developing a real-time monitoring scheme and data management procedures, using modern techniques and biodiversity indicators as sentinels to promptly identify potential threats and short-term changes to the marine environment, taking into consideration climate change projections.
- Propose the **extension and replicability of the monitoring scheme to other EU Mediterranean countries**, through networking and transferability activities.
- Identify the spatial extent of the main threats for the target species and their habitats and produce **species-specific risk maps** for the target species.
- Establish a **Marine Conservation Task Force in Greece**, consisting of well-trained site managers and officers of NECCA who will further coordinate the implementation of biodiversity-related activities of the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) and N2K monitoring / management in the MOBI sites of Greece and Italy.
- Ensure the transferability and continuity of the project's results and outputs by **training at least 100 site managers and decision-makers in Greece, Italy and other Eastern Mediterranean countries**.

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- Carry out an **extensive networking and stakeholders' involvement campaign**, to ensure the incorporation of the project's recommendations and results in various levels of national and international decision-making processes.
- Promote the results and outcomes of the project to the lay public through dedicated **public awareness activities**.

2.3 Area of Implementation

The project's conservation actions will be implemented in both the Ionian Sea and Aegean Seas, as well as in the Greek Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ), covering the offshore areas of Greece.

Additional survey work and telemetry will be carried out in three Italian N2K sites, exclusively for assessing the interactions between seabird target species, which nest in Italian sites, and forage in Greek foraging grounds of the project area. Some actions of the project will be focused in the N2K project sites, while others will be implemented in the wider project area (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Map of the project area of implementation.

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The project sites consist of the following Special Areas of Conservation (SACs) / Sites of Community Importance (SCIs) and Special Protection Areas (SPAs):

- **Greece:** GR1110013, GR1150014, GR1430004, GR1430005, GR2110001, GR2210002, GR2210004, GR2220003, GR2220007, GR2230004, GR2230008, GR2310001, GR2330005, GR2330008, GR2420009, GR2420016, GR2530007, GR2540002, GR2540003, GR2550005, GR2550010, GR3000012, GR3000019, GR4210001, GR4210003, GR4210011, GR4210021, GR4210023, GR4210025, GR4210028, GR4220006, GR4220021, GR4220027, GR4220033, GR4310004, GR4320006, GR4320011, GR4330004, GR4340003, GR4340013, GR4340024, in total 41 N2K sites (Appendix II).
- **Italy:** IT9110040, IT9120012, IT9150015, in total 3 N2K sites (see Appendix II for the names and types of N2K sites).

2.4 Target Species

The Mediterranean basin is considered a region of conflicts and intensive human activities for millennia. It is also a Sea of Nature, a global biodiversity hotspot, presently under pressure from several threats. The LIFE MareNatura Project aims to provide the means for the mitigation of threats for nine (9) of the most threatened EU priority species of seabirds, marine turtles and marine mammals.

The Project Area [including 41 N2K sites in the Aegean Sea, the Ionian Sea and the Greek Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ), as well as 3 N2K sites in Italy], with an acreage of more than 48M ha, covers a considerable part of the Mediterranean basin and is a unique marine area in the EU context as it supports very significant percentages of the EU populations of the LIFE MareNatura target species (Figure 2).

In particular, it holds:

- more than **70% of the Mediterranean Monk Seal** (*Monachus monachus*) [Annexes II & IV of the Habitats Directive (HD), Vulnerable in the IUCN Global Red List (GRL), Critically Endangered in the European Red List (ERL) and the Greek Red Data Book (GRDB)],
- more than **86% of the Loggerhead Turtle** (*Caretta caretta*) (Annexes II & IV of the HD, Vulnerable in the IUCN GRL, Endangered in the GRDB),

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- the only **developmental habitat of the Green Turtle** (*Chelonia mydas*) (Annex IV of the HD, Endangered in the IUCN GRL, Endangered in the GRDB),
- **95% of the Mediterranean population of Sperm Whale** (*Physeter macrocephalus*), which is considered to be genetically distinct [Annex IV of the HD, Vulnerable in the ERL, Endangered in the Mediterranean Red List (MRL) and the GRDB)],
- **100% of the Mediterranean population of Harbor Porpoise** (*Phocoena phocoena*) (Annexes II & IV of the HD, Vulnerable in the ERL, Endangered in the GRDB),
- a significant but yet **undefined percentage of the Cuvier's Beaked Whale** (*Ziphius cavirostris*) (Annex IV of the HD, Data Deficient in the ERL, MRL and GRDB),
- more than **3% of the Common Dolphin** (*Delphinus delphis*), (Annex IV of the HD, Data Deficient in the ERL, Endangered in the MRL and the GRDB),
- more than **35% (35% breeding and >85% of foraging habitats) of the Yelkouan Shearwater** (*Puffinus yelkouan*) (Annex I of the Birds Directive (BD), Vulnerable in the ERL, Near Threatened in the GRDB), and
- more than **4% of the Audouin's Gull** (*Larus audouinii*) (Annex I of the BD, Vulnerable in the ERL, Vulnerable in the GRDB).

Monachus monachus

Caretta caretta

Chelonia mydas

Physeter macrocephalus

Phocoena phocoena

Ziphius cavirostris

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Delphinus delphis

Puffinus yelkouan

Larus audouinii

Figure 2. Target species of the LIFE MareNatura project.

2.5 Means of Achievement - Work Packages and Tasks

The LIFE MareNatura project objectives will be achieved through the implementation of six (6) Work Packages (WPs) that will enable effective project implementation, namely:

- I. The overall **project coordination and management**. It will ensure timely and efficient project implementation following the LIFE Program provisions and the project Grant Agreement (WP1).
- II. The setting up and implementation of:
 - a. a **cost-effective methodology for ecological surveys** for the target species across their distribution range within the project area,
 - b. a **comprehensive and updated marine biodiversity hotspots inventory** (MOBI),
 - c. a well-justified and scientifically documented **proposal for the hotspots within the Greek territorial waters and the Greek EEZ**, to be designated as new marine sites in the N2K network of Greece, and
 - d. a detailed Management Guidelines with preliminary / refined **Site-Specific Conservation Objectives (SSCOs)**, for them as well as for the project sites [Objective (a)] (WP2).
- III. The use of the evidence produced by the ecological surveys and models for effective **Maritime Spatial Planning** (MSP) to map and alleviate the major threats affecting the target species [Objective (b)] (WP3), based on the principles of Systematic Conservation Planning (SCP).
- IV. The sustainability, transferability and replication of the project results, taking advantage of the experience and know-how

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gathered by WP2 & WP3, to plan an effective **Integrated Monitoring Scheme**, including an Early Warning System (EWS) for threats, for the offshore and onshore sites, to be implemented by the **NECCA Marine Task Force**, related to the target species SSCOs [Objectives (c) & (d)]. The WP will also contain the **Marine Conservation School, stakeholders' involvement** and **international policy collaboration** for the conservation of marine biodiversity hotspots in international waters and the achievement of the EU Biodiversity Strategy and Athens Declaration objectives for the Mediterranean Sea [Objective (e)] (WP4).

- V. The implementation of a wide **public awareness and communication campaign** to further disseminate the project approach within the 2 project countries and the Mediterranean region [Objective (e)] (WP5).
- VI. The **monitoring and evaluation of the project's impact** (WP6).

Each Work Package is structured in specific Tasks (T) as follows (Figure 3):

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Figure 3. LIFE MareNatura Project Work Packages (WPs) and Tasks (Ts).

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2.6 Deliverables and Expected Outcomes

Several deliverables have been foreseen during the implementation of the project, serving as elements of output within the scope of the project. The complete breakdown of the LIFE MareNatura Project deliverables per Work Package is listed below in Table 1.

After the completion of the project, a series of important outcomes related to the objectives of the project are expected (Figure 4):

Figure 4. The LIFE MareNatura Project expected outcomes.

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Table 1. Deliverables per Work Package (WP) of the LIFE MareNatura Project, including Lead Beneficiary and due date.

Work Package	Deliverable	Lead Beneficiary	Due date (month)
WP 1. Project Management and Coordination	D1.1 Project Guidelines Document (PGD)	HCMR	2
	D1.2 1 st Year Report on cumulative expenditure	HCMR	6
	D1.3 2 nd Year Report on cumulative expenditure	HCMR	18
	D1.4 3 rd Year Report on cumulative expenditure	HCMR	30
	D1.5 Progress Report	HCMR	34
	D1.6 4 th Year Report on cumulative expenditure	HCMR	42
	D1.7 5 th Year Report on cumulative expenditure	HCMR	54
	D1.8 6 th Year Report on cumulative expenditure	HCMR	66
	D1.9 Audit Report	HCMR	72
WP 2: Identification of Marine Biodiversity Hotspots	D2.1 Technical & Data Management Plan	NCC	6
	D2.2 Surveys' Inventory	HCMR	36
	D2.3 Marine Biodiversity Hotspots inventory	HCMR	48
	D2.4 Preliminary proposal for marine areas to be included in the N2K network	NCC	48
	D2.5 Preliminary SSCOs & Management Guidelines for the candidate offshore N2K sites.	NECCA	60
WP 3: Development of a Decision Support Tool (DST)	D3.1 Conservation plans	UAegean	58
	D3.2 Climate change impact assessment on Marine Biodiversity	NOA	48
WP 4: Sustainability, Replication and Exploitation of Project Results	D4.1 Replicability and Transferability Plan	NECCA	6
	D4.2 Integrated Monitoring Plan	NCC	36
	D4.3 Marine Conservation School (MCS) GPGs	NECCA	48
	D4.4 After-LIFE Conservation Plan	HCMR	60
WP 5: Dissemination and Communication of the Project	D5.1 Leaflet & Banner/Beach flags & T-shirts	UoC	12
	D5.2 Guide book	UoC	24
	D5.3 Videos	MEDASS ET	24
	D5.4 School toolkit	HCMR	36
	D5.5 Layman's Report	HCMR	60
	D5.6 Webpage	UoC	9
WP 6: Monitoring and Evaluation of the Project	D6.1 Extract of the project data from the LIFE KPI webtool	HCMR	9
	D6.2 Extract of the project data from the LIFE KPI webtool - final	HCMR	72

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2.7 Project Consortium

The LIFE MareNatura Project is implemented by a large consortium consisting of twelve (12) partners, i.e. the Natural Environment and Climate Change Agency (NECCA), the University of the Aegean (UoA), the University of Crete (UoC), the National Observatory of Athens (NOA), the Hellenic Ornithological Society - BirdLife Greece (HOS), the Hellenic Society for the Study and Protection of the Monk Seal (MOM), the Sea Turtle Protection Society of Greece (ARCHELON), the Mediterranean Association to Save the Sea Turtles (MEDASSET), the Nature Conservation Consultants (NCC), the Italian Institute for Environmental Protection and Research (ISPRA), and the Waterproof Marine Consultancy and Services B.V., under the coordination of the Hellenic Centre for Marine Research (HCMR).

The **Hellenic Centre for Marine Research (HCMR)** is the largest marine research centre in Greece and it comprises 3 Institutes that cover almost all disciplines of marine research: the Institute of Marine Biology, Biotechnology and Aquaculture (IMBBC), the Institute of Marine Biological Resources and Inland Waters (IMBRIW) and the Institute of Oceanography (IO). HCMR has a long expertise in studying marine ecosystems and has coordinated several international projects, including LIFE, European as well as national projects.

The **Natural Environment and Climate Change Agency (NECCA)** is a newly established public body governed by private law, operating under the supervision of the Hellenic Ministry of Environment and Energy. It is the sole successor of the National Centre of Environment and Sustainable Development (NCESD) and the former Management Bodies of Protected Areas.

The **University of Crete (UoC)** was established in 1973. Currently, over 14,000 undergraduates and 2,500 postgraduate students are registered. The **Natural History Museum of Crete (NHMC)** holds extensive experience in biodiversity conservation projects, especially in LIFE projects for biodiversity conservation in both mainland and coastal Greece. It has collaborated on many projects with HOS, NCC and the Hellenic Ministry of Environment & Energy, as well as with project partners from Europe.

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Research in the Department of Marine Sciences at the **University of the Aegean (UoA)** covers a broad range of subjects, from marine biology and conservation to marine geology, physical and chemical oceanography, remote sensing, hydroacoustic technology and climate change. The Marine Biodiversity and Ecosystems Management lab has long experience in benthic ecology, biodiversity and conservation, ecosystem functioning and health, and has conducted many relevant projects.

The **National Observatory of Athens (NOA)** is the oldest public research centre in Greece (founded in 1842), supervised by the General Secretariat for Research and Innovation. The Institute for Environmental Research and Sustainable Development (IERSD) / Climate & Climate Change Group has extensive experience in providing climate change (impact) projections to the EU and it is (inter-)nationally funded. The IERSD Research Group has the expertise and all the required tools and methodologies to analyze data and climate models using climate indicators, for supervising the climate change projections and updates in adequate scale for the DST.

The **Hellenic Ornithological Society (HOS)** was founded in 1982 and is a Non-Governmental, nation-wide, non-profit Organization, the only one in Greece that works exclusively for the protection of wild birds and their habitats. HOS is BirdLife International's national partner in Greece. It aims to study and protect wild birds and their habitats in Greece, provide scientific information and data to the Greek Government and the European Union, and inform, educate and sensitize the public. HOS was responsible for identifying and updating the Important Bird Areas in Greece and has promoted and advocated the designation of the majority of these IBAs as SPA, in collaboration with BirdLife International.

The **Hellenic Society for the Study and Protection of the Monk Seal (MOM)** is a non-profit, non-governmental organization established in 1988. Today, 8,500 members from Greece and abroad support the activities of the organization, and since 1996 it has been accepted as a member of IUCN. MOM's mission statement is the protection of marine and coastal environments, focusing on the critically endangered Mediterranean monk seal. Tools to accomplish

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the latter include the design and activation of an institutional framework as well as information and public awareness among citizens and social groups. These tools must be based on and substantiated by concrete scientific evidence.

The **Sea Turtle Protection Society of Greece (ARCHELON)**, was established in 1983 and it is a non-profit association aiming at the conservation of sea turtles and their habitats in Greece. Its main activities are monitoring and research, rescue and rehabilitation of sick and injured turtles and raising public awareness. ARCHELON is a Partner of the UNEP / Mediterranean Action Plan and a member of the European Union for the Conservation of the Coasts (EUCC). Members of ARCHELON participate in the IUCN / Marine Turtle Specialist Group and contribute to the formulation of the international strategy for the conservation of sea turtles.

The **Mediterranean Association to Save the Sea Turtles (MEDASSET)** was founded in 1988 in England and 1993 in Greece, having as its core mission to contribute to the conservation and protection of sea turtles in their natural habitats throughout the Mediterranean. MEDASSET is an international NGO registered as a not-for-profit organization in Greece. MEDASSET works under the main themes of sea turtles, coastal & marine habitats, Marine Protected Areas, fisheries interaction, sustainable and responsible tourism, litter & pollution, sustainable coastal & offshore development, climate change and maritime traffic impact mitigation.

The **Nature Conservation Consultants (NCC)** is an ecological consultancy focusing on the conservation of nature and biodiversity. It was founded in July 2010 by a group of experienced scientists specialized in nature conservation, in particular wild birds and their habitats. The consultancy is active in a variety of fields related to the study and protection of the natural environment, extending from the implementation of conservation actions for the improvement of protected species state within or outside Natura 2000 network sites in the framework of projects such as the European LIFE projects and the implementation of biodiversity monitoring projects in protected areas to the development of Appropriate Assessments for the environmental licensing of small and major infrastructure and the preparation of management plans for protected areas.

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The **Italian Institute for Environmental Protection and Research (ISPRA)** acts under the vigilance and policy guidance of MASE, the Italian Ministry of Environment and Energy Security (formerly MiTE - Ministero per la Transizione Ecologica). The Department involved in the project is engaged in research and support to MASE for monitoring, protection and restoration of natural habitats and fauna.

WaterProof Marine Consultancy and Services B.V. is an international specialized consultancy firm for the marine sector. It focuses on specialized coastal & marine consultancy as well as related services for the offshore industry. From a wide range, the consultancy advises clients in the preparation and implementation phase of projects at sea and in the coastal zone. With a combination of key theoretical knowledge and solid practical experience, it offers high-end and solution-driven products for its clients.

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Chapter 3. LIFE MareNatura Replicability and Transferability Plan

3.1 Replicability Transferability Plan (RTP): What is it and why do we need it?

One of the key outcomes expected from projects receiving LIFE funding is the dissemination of knowledge and experience gained throughout the project to a broader audience within and beyond the implementation area. Thereby, specific modules employed in each project are recommended to be replicated and transferred to other locations. To effectively disseminate project outcomes, the engaged partners are encouraged to create a Replicability and Transferability Plan (RTP), aligned with LIFE requisites, that outlines explicit strategies and mechanisms.

On one hand, **“Replication”** refers to the procedure of reproducing different, successfully implemented modules of a project such as actions, methodologies/tools, techniques, models, protocols, good practices, or recommendations identically and for the same objective to be applied by other interested parties and/or countries. Therefore, this exact process ensures the engagement of additional regions and/or particular users to multiply the project’s impact, identifying and anticipating at the same time emerging issues and similar challenges.

This approach can:

- significantly reduce the amount of time and effort required to create a new project,
- contribute to a collective understanding of effective conservation strategies,
- influence and shape relevant policies,
- encourage other stakeholders to adopt similar actions,
- foster partnerships between different entities,
- strengthen the existing stakeholders’ network, and
- build opportunities for new collaborations on future initiatives.

On the other hand, **“Transferability”** refers to the ability of knowledge, technologies, methodologies, or solutions developed and implemented in a specific project to be transferred and applied in different contexts, locations, or settings. Transferability focuses on the adaptability and

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relevance of the project outcomes beyond the original scope and geographical area. The goal is to leverage the knowledge and experiences gained from a particular project and apply them in diverse circumstances to address similar challenges. Therefore, transferability is closely related to replicability, but it extends beyond simply duplicating a project in another location. It involves understanding the underlying principles and mechanisms of a successful project and tailoring them to suit the unique conditions of a new setting.

The current document addresses and elaborates on the content of the RTP as part of LIFE22-NAT-EL-LIFE MareNatura Project: “Conservation of priority species of marine megafauna in Greece and Italy” (Project: 101113792 - LIFE22-NAT-EL-LIFE MareNatura - LIFE-2022-SAP-NAT), in the context of Deliverable D4.1 of Work Package 4: Sustainability, Replication and Exploitation of Project Results.

The RTP mainly highlights the features of project implementation, while also including the definition of principal RTP objectives, the identification and consultation of the targeted stakeholders at a national, regional and international level aiming to the preparation of relevant guidelines, the suitable innovative actions to be replicated / transferred to maximize the replicability and transferability of the project’s results, the concrete methods to facilitate replication / transfer, and the identification of financial sources for replication / transfer.

The upcoming RTP, which is based on the project’s proposal and has to be delivered by the end of month 7 (M7) of the project (January 2024), will act as an essential guide for integrating transferability and replicability actions, both during project’s implementation and after its completion. Additionally, it will facilitate the preparation, preservation, and dissemination of crucial information regarding the actions to be replicated and transferred.

The refinement and finalization of the RTP are essential to the project's success, and we plan to leverage the invaluable insights gained during the current project implementation to achieve this.

3.2 Overview of the LIFE MareNatura RTP Methodology

The RTP was led by NECCA, which is the lead beneficiary of Deliverable

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4.1 “Replicability and Transferability Plan”, with the collaboration of the Technical Facilitation, the Policy and the Communication Teams of the LIFE MareNatura consortium. HCMR, ISPRA, NCC, UoC and MEDASSET also contributed in current Deliverable.

For the preparation of the RTP, the structure and the contents were initially determined to maximize the efficiency of the Plan. Then the framework of the methodology applied for the development of the current RTP was set in a 6-steps approach (Figure 5), as follows:

Step 1. Define RTP objectives

The basic aim of the LIFE MareNatura RTP is to ensure that the outputs and the methods implemented will be able to be replicated by interested parties of the project or other Mediterranean countries. Specific objectives are set to ensure the success of the results.

Step 2. Select Project Actions for Replication and Transfer

Four specific actions of the LIFE MareNatura project were selected for replication and transfer. These are:

- i. The multidimensional approach for assessing the target species population size and density in project sites by applying various state-of-the-art census techniques and abundance surveys.
- ii. The development of a Decision Support Tool (DST) for SCP to improve the decision-making process regarding nature conservation strategies.
- iii. The establishment of a Marine Conservation Task Force (MCTF) to coordinate the implementation of biodiversity-related monitoring / management activities.
- iv. The identification of the MOBI of the target species hotspots to promote the conservation of ABNJ in international conventions and agreements, through devoted advocacy actions.

Step 3. Define Spatial Implementation of the RTP

In this step, the geographical reach potential of the RTP is defined. This includes, apart from the participating countries, neighbouring countries in the Eastern Mediterranean and the Black Sea.

Step 4. Identify Stakeholders

To effectively implement replication actions, it is crucial to involve competent authorities and specific targeted groups. The interested parties that could replicate the project’s outputs and methodologies were

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identified at local, regional, national and international levels.

Step 5. Specify RTP Tools and define Time Planning

The RTP specifies the tools that will be used for the efficient transfer of experience gained through the project's implementation to the interested parties, as well as between them after replication. This will be achieved through training, active participation in actions, and consultations to examine their needs and capacities. To determine the implementation time-frame for the project, careful consideration was given to the project deliverables and targeted audiences as outlined in the project's proposal.

Step 6. Propose Funding / Financial Sources

Financial sources and possible funding programs are proposed, for the replication of the project actions, tailored to the different stakeholders categorized by types of funding.

Figure 5. The LIFE MareNatura Replicability and Transferability methodology flowchart.

3.3 RTP Objectives

The basic aim of the RTP is to make the LIFE MareNatura Project better known, and above all to highlight the instruments that will be created, tested and evaluated as effective and worth being both replicated and transferred. Additionally, it acts as a mean for these actions to be widely accepted and adopted by agencies, public authorities / organizations and bodies concerned with marine megafauna's conservation.

Especially, the RTP is focused on the sustainability, replicability and transferability of the project through: i) the establishment and pilot implementation of the Integrated Monitoring Plan (IMP), ii) the establishment of a Marine Conservation Task Force (MCTF), that will

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further coordinate the implementation of biodiversity-related activities of the MSFD and the N2K monitoring and management in offshore areas of Greece, and iii) the implementation of a Marine Conservation School (MCS) demonstrating best practice techniques.

At the same time, the RTP will ensure the extension of the IMP to other EU and non-EU Mediterranean countries and the transferability and continuity of the project's results and outputs, through the mobilization of other regional networks and advocating for the integration of biodiversity hotspots into the N2K network in collaboration with regional and international actors and the establishment of MARBIONET, a Mediterranean network of marine biodiversity academics and NGOs.

3.4 Selectable Project Actions for Replication and Transfer

Four (4) actions of the project were selected for replication and transfer out of the numerous actions included in the six (6) Work Packages of the LIFE MareNatura Project. In the context of the current project, the selection process has been influenced by a range of factors, including political, economic, social, and cultural considerations. Hence, the RTP prioritize the project actions that contribute to building the capacity of the receiving countries, particularly by strengthening institutions, developing skills, and empowering local communities to address challenges independently in the long term.

These are detailed in the sub-sections below.

3.4.1 Multidimensional Approach for target species monitoring (WP2)

The LIFE MareNatura Project seeks to leverage recent advances in telemetry, bio-logging technologies and other large-scale biodiversity survey techniques in the marine environment. The goal is to develop a cost-effective methodology for conducting ecological surveys of the target species across their distribution range within the project area.

With the 44 project N2K sites as starting points, and focusing on the support of the 9 target species, the LIFE MareNatura Project will pioneer the engagement of all expert groups involved in marine research and conservation on a large geographical scale. This will entail a

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comprehensive integration of state-of-the-art and traditional ecological techniques. These techniques include large-scale telemetry, extensive aerial surveys (by light aircraft and drones), boat surveys employing Marine Mammal Observations (MMOs) and European Seabirds At Sea (ESAS) observers, high-definition marine surveillance radars, underwater acoustic sensors and bio-acoustic devices, as well as extensive biological sampling on breeding colonies and other sites important for the target species. Additionally, eDNA sampling will be employed to generate, through species-specific molecular assays, abundance estimates for the target species and identify their critical foraging and congregation grounds, as well as movement and migration corridors within the project area.

3.4.2 Decision Support Tool for Systematic Conservation Planning (WP3)

Based on the ecological evidence that will be collected in the framework of Work Package 2, a Decision Support Tool for Systematic Conservation Planning (SCP) to facilitate Maritime Spatial Planning (MSP) will be developed. The tool will identify spatial zones for allocating space for marine uses, considering the ecological importance and the sensitivity of the marine areas, as well as the various economic activities and their impact. Climatic predictions at a fine scale will be used to model the impact of climate change.

The SCP is defined as a structured stepwise approach to mapping conservation area networks, with proper feedback, revision and reiteration at any stage. Our approach will build up on the existing N2K sites, aiming to address the low representation of oceanic habitats in the current network and will take advantage of the production of tracking and logging data, to feed an expanded version of the model applied, which uses MARXAN with Zones to generate alternative MSP, including relevant human uses and their cumulative impact on a wide set of key biodiversity features.

Four (4) important economic activities will be included in the analysis to represent opportunity cost: i) commercial fishing, ii) touristic development, iii) energy production / transfer activities, and iv) marine traffic.

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3.4.3 Marine Conservation Task Force (WP4)

Upon project initiation, NECCA will form the Marine Conservation Task Force (MCTF), comprising marine biodiversity officers from NECCA's pool of permanent staff and experts contracted throughout the project's duration. MCTF's members will be placed in various NECCA Protected Areas Management Units (PAMUs). In collaboration with the Coordinating Beneficiary and the project partners, they will actively participate in the fieldwork carried out on project sites, species nesting locations and colonies, as well as pelagic habitats and also in telemetry activities. During the first years of the project, MCTF members will acquire appropriate training in field activities from the partners' field experts, and after the third year of the project, they will take over the responsibility of the survey and field conservation activities of the project. They will also participate in field conservation actions of the project partners, to acquire appropriate training for species conservation as well as systematic theoretical and practical training through the Marine Conservation School (MCS).

One of the main tasks of the MCTF will be to participate in the development and coordination of the Early Warning System (EWS) and the Integrated Monitoring Plan (IMP). It is expected that MCTF will become the core team of NECCA for the monitoring and conservation of marine and coastal sites in Greece, transferring the experience and know-how to the Protected Areas Management Units (PAMUs) of NECCA and further improving the operational capacity of the organization concerning the conservation of coastal and marine habitats of the target species. The members of the MCTF will also participate in the project's thematic workshops, training sessions for the use of new technologies, and data management activities to acquire relevant experience.

3.4.4 Identification of the Mediterranean Offshore Biodiversity Inventory (MOBI) of the target species hot spots

The Areas Beyond National Jurisdiction (ABNJ), i.e. the areas outside territorial waters which do not fall within a mutually agreed Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ), will be considered for the identification of the target species' biodiversity hotspots in the context of the LIFE MareNatura Project. These areas are either located in the Aegean Sea beyond the 6 nautical miles of territorial waters area or the southern part

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of the project area, where, although EEZs remain to be agreed with neighbouring countries, Greece is regularly reporting for Articles 12 & 17 of the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS). For these areas, there are no N2K areas defined at the moment. However, several internationally identified hotspots like the Important Marine Mammal Areas (IMMAs), candidate IMMAs (cIMMAs) and Areas of Interest (Aols) exist in ABNJ.

The LIFE MareNatura Project aims to include within MOBI 10-20% of ABNJ coverage in the project area. For these areas, besides the aerial surveys that will provide valuable distribution data for the target species, precious data will also be collected by telemetry activities, especially from seabirds, marine turtles and sperm whales. The project will further promote the conservation of the MOBI hotspots located in ABNJs in International Conventions and Agreements, aiming at further improving their conservation status, by collaborating and motivating international actors and treaties. Efforts will be made for these hotspots to be included in a scientific catalogue for further use by International / Regional Organizations, Conventions and Agreements.

3.5 Spatial Implementation of the RTP

The LIFE MareNatura Project is focused in the Aegean Sea, the Ionian Sea, the Greek Exclusive Economic Zones (EEZs), and the 3 N2K sites located in Italy, which cover a vast expanse of over 48 million hectares. Furthermore, through replicability and transferability processes, there is a possibility of expanding the project area to encompass marine regions of the rest of the Mediterranean Sea, including both EU and non-EU countries, along with countries in the Black Sea.

It is suggested that the proposed measures should be replicated on a state-wide basis, taking also into consideration the specific political, legal, social, economic, and technological conditions of each region. This approach would ensure that the implementation is feasible across the entire territory of a given country. By adapting the measures to the aforementioned conditions, a tailored implementation approach can be developed that would be more effective in achieving the desired outcomes. Furthermore, it is crucial to incorporate neighbouring countries into the RTP. Apart from Greece and Italy (the participating countries), this would encompass the Southeastern Mediterranean countries such as

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Cyprus, Egypt, Israel, Jordan, Palestine, Turkey, Lebanon, the State of Libya, the Syrian Arab Republic, and Tunisia, the Balkan coastal countries like Albania, Bulgaria, Croatia, Montenegro, and Romania, as well as other Mediterranean countries such as Malta (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Spatial implementation of the LIFE MareNatura Project's Replicability and Transferability Plan (countries of the project are highlighted with yellow fond, RTP countries with diagonal green lines, countries of the project which are also potential RTP countries are highlighted with diagonal yellow lines). The map was produced in QGIS version 3.28.13.

3.6 Identification of Stakeholders

It is imperative to involve also specific targeted groups to effectively implement replication actions. Gaining their support and securing a commitment to collaborate, through informative, educational and awareness-raising initiatives, is essential for the success of the proposed tools. This will ultimately lead to an improvement of the current

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deficiencies in marine conservation targeted by these tools.

In the quest to identify entities capable of replicating or transferring the innovative actions of the LIFE MareNatura Project, we considered a comprehensive list of Greek stakeholders developed by WWF Hellas within the LIFE-IP 4 Natura Project (LIFE16 IPE/GR/000002), as well as an Italian stakeholders list suggested by the project's Italian partner, ISPRA. The RTP is designed to cater to a broad range of target groups, including among others: tourism professionals, professional and recreational fishers' associations, diving centres and associations, the general public, all sea users and interested parties, as well as of stakeholders including: ministries and agencies, chambers, universities and research institutions, authorities responsible for Natura 2000 management, authorities regulating fishing activities, authorities responsible for energy and renewables, and NGOs involved in marine conservation.

The list of stakeholders will undergo refinement and finalization, leveraging the invaluable insights gained through the current project implementation. Furthermore, we will duly consider the project collaboration and interactions with diverse authorities, entities, and affiliations at national, regional and international level that have been forged throughout the project's lifespan. In **Appendix I**, further details concerning the potential stakeholders per region relevant to marine conservation are included.

3.7 Tools to Enable Replicability and Transferability

Several activities will be carried out by the LIFE MareNatura Project, such as workshops, conferences, capacity-building training, and communication campaigns, to achieve the primary aim of the project and its specific objectives. These actions will also support and facilitate the objectives of the current RTP.

Based on the project's proposal these activities include:

(a) Thematic workshops

The project will organize thematic workshops to transfer the Integrated Monitoring Plan (IMP) (WP4 / T.4.3) approach to other Mediterranean countries. The transfer of the IMP approach will be the subject of two (2) workshops to be organized during the last 2 years of the project, inviting participants from EU Mediterranean countries. The monitoring methods,

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platforms, data management and transfer issues will be presented and discussed. Experts from IUCN and BirdLife International will be invited to provide their vision and expertise for the further transfer of the project's approach. Also, during the last year of the project, a workshop will be organized aiming at organizations and experts working with megafauna in the Eastern Mediterranean and Black Sea regions (WP4 / T.4.6), i.e. areas which support significant foraging, wintering and migration grounds of the Greek and Italian megafauna species but are not included in the current proposal. The workshop will be dedicated to the transfer of knowledge from all stages of the process - from data collection, data management and analysis, identification of marine hotspots and finally MPA designation.

(b) Training sessions

Training sessions will be taking place to train the Marine Conservation Task Force members (WP4 / T.4.5) in the use of new technologies (e.g. drone sampling, thermal camera monitoring, radar surveys, biological sampling) and to the data management activities to acquire relevant experience. Furthermore, through the establishment and operation of the Marine Conservation School (MCS), the project will contribute to the capacity building and training of NECCA staff to ensure the sustainable conservation of the project sites and biodiversity hotspots. Officers of other stakeholders involved in the target species conservation, monitoring and management (e.g. NGO staff, fishers' associations, ecotourism guides, and diving centers' personnel) will be invited to participate.

(c) Communication and dissemination activities

The project's communication and dissemination activities will also intend to identify and take advantage of synergies with other initiatives and projects, as well as to capitalize on the project's deliverables and management tools and methods for marine biodiversity conservation. A 2-day Mediterranean Conference will be organized to promote the project's outputs, foster knowledge sharing and networking, and highlight the way forward. In addition, special focus will be given to the implementation of awareness activities for schools, to familiarize young children with marine megafauna, the associated threats and the necessary actions to conserve the species populations. Specialized material including leaflets, applications, videos and movies will be produced for this purpose and actions will be planned along with

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educators to ensure learning in a playful and interactive way, addressing various age groups.

(d) Public awareness and communication campaign

Overall, the LIFE MareNatura Project will implement a wide public awareness and communication campaign to further disseminate the project's approach within the 2 project countries and the Mediterranean region (WP5). The main objective of the project's communication campaign will be to widely spread the project's results among the main target groups, the general public and the broader stakeholders' community (policy makers, academia, competent authorities, etc.), as well as facilitating knowledge transfer, community engagement and acceptance, and maximizing the opportunities for exploitation.

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3.8 Time Planning

Activities for replicability and transferability must be planned in a timeframe depending on the project's Deliverables and the targeted audience. The LIFE MareNatura RTP takes a long-term view and ensures that each activity is executed over a sufficient duration to achieve the optimal desired results.

The time planning of each LIFE MareNatura RTP activity is shown in the following Gantt chart (Table 2). In case the project schedule is extended, adjustments may be made accordingly.

Table 2. Gantt chart for time planning of the LIFE MareNatura Replicability and Transferability Plan (RTP).

RTP Activity	1st year	2nd year	3rd year	4th year	5th year	6th year	After-LIFE period
T.4.3 [Development and Implementation of an Integrated Monitoring Plan]							
T.4.4 [Implementation of a Marine Conservation School demonstrating best practice techniques]							
T.4.5 [Establishment of a Marine Conservation Task Force]							
T.4.6 [MARBIONET: Establishment of an EU Mediterranean network of marine biodiversity academics and NGOs]							
T.4.7 [Collaboration with national, regional and international bodies and actors]							
T.5.2 [Overall project communication]							
T.5.4 [International conference]							

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3.9 Funding / Financial Sources

The financial resources and funding for the replication of the proposed actions can be sought either from National Funds, European Structural Funds for EU member states, or from horizontal European Funds, bilateral or multilateral State Agreements, private foundations, international organizations or NGOs depending on the entities and the projects applying, as well as the area of implementation.

The following proposed funding sources on the national level refer mainly to Greece. European funding can be sought by all EU member states, while Partnership Programs and International Organizations' funding categories can be explored also by non-EU countries. The main funding sources proposed are the following:

I. National Funding and EU Structural Funds

- [Green Fund](#)
- [National Recovery and Resilience Plan](#)
- [NSRF2021-2027](#)
- Public Investment Fund
- Regional Funds

II. European funding

- [European Cooperation in Science and Technology](#)
- [European Maritime Fisheries and Aquaculture Fund](#)
- [LIFE funding instrument](#)
- [European Regional Development Fund](#)
- [Horizon Europe](#)

III. Partnership programs

- [EEA and Norway Grants Funding](#)
- [EU Interreg Program](#)
- [Interreg NEXT Black Sea Basin Program](#)

IV. International Organizations/ NGOs/ Foundations and other sources

- [The Med Fund](#)
- [The Monk Sea Alliance](#)
- [A.G. Leventis Foundation](#)
- [Global Environment Facility \(GEF\)](#)
- [A.C. Laskaridis Charitable Foundation](#)
- [Blue Marine Foundation](#)
- [Ocean Care](#)
- [MIO-ECSDE](#)
- [Bodossaki Foundation](#)

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Appendix I: LIFE MareNatura Replicability and Transferability Plan - Stakeholders List

ALBANIA
Albanian Center for Marine Research
Albanian Ornithological Society (AOS)
Institute for Nature Conservation in Albania (INCA)
Interinstitutional Maritime Operational Centre (IMOC)
Ministry of Infrastructure and Energy, General Maritime Directorate
Ministry of Tourism and Environment
National Agency of Protected Areas
UNDP in Albania
BULGARIA
Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Institute of Oceanology
Bulgarian Biodiversity Foundation
Bulgarian Society for the Protection of Birds
Green Balkans
Ministry of Environment and Waters
Ministry of Transport, Information Technologies and Communications, Maritime Administration Executive Agency
CROATIA
Association BIOM, Zagreb
Croatian Agency for Environment and Nature, Zagreb
Croatian Natural History Museum, Zagreb
Institute of Oceanography and Fisheries (Split)
Institute of Tourism, Zagreb
Ministry of Maritime Affairs, Transport and Infrastructure
Natura - Society for nature protection of Croatia, Zagreb
Ruđer Bošković Institute, Center for Marine Research (CMR)
Telascica Nature Park Public Institution
University of Dubrovnik - Institute for Marine and Coastal Research (IMP-DU)
University of Zagreb - Division of Biology
CYPRUS
Birdlife Cyprus
Cyprus Marine and Maritime Institute (CMMI)
Cyprus Ports Authority
Cyprus Wildlife Research Institute
Marine and Environmental Research (MER) Lab
Ministry of Agriculture Rural Development and Environment, Department of Fisheries and Marine Research

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Open University and Cyprus Technical University
Shipping Deputy Ministry
Society for the Protection of Turtles (SPOT)
University of Cyprus - Department of Biological Sciences, Oceanography Center
EGYPT
Dahab Marine Research Centre
Ministry of Environment
Ministry of Transportation
Nature Conservation Egypt (NCE)
GREECE
Aegean Greeners
Aegean Rebreath
Aetolian Landscape and Environment Protection Company
Agricultural University of Athens - Animal Production and Aquaculture Science
Agrimi - Hellenic Center for the Management and Protection of Wild Fauna and Habitats
All For Blue
ANIMA - Wildlife Protection Association
Animal Rescue Lemnos
Archipelagos - Institute of Marine Conservation
Aristotle University of Thessaloniki - Department of Biology, Department of Civil Engineering
Association for Environmental Protection and Tourist Development of Aegialia "KORINTHIAKOS"
Association for Environmental Protection of Corfu
Association for the Care and Protection of Wild Animals on Paros Island
Association of Coastal Fishing Boat Owners of Greece
Association of Ecology and Environment of Chios
Association of Friends of Diving Parks "TRIDENTSTAR"
Association of Greek Tourist Boat Owners
Association of Nafpaktos Friends of the Environment "EPIVIOSI"
Association of Shipping Shipowners
Chamber of Environment & Sustainability
CISD - Citizens Inspectorate for Sustainable Development
Citizen Intervention Group on Environmental Issues
Citizens for Nature
Citizens for the Rights of Nature and Life

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Company for the Study and Protection of the Environment of the Prefecture of Magnesia
Corfu Environmental Protection Association
Decentralized Administrations - Regions of Greece, Directorates of Environment and Spatial Planning, Directorates of Water, Directorates of Industry, Energy and Natural Resources, Directorates of Development and Environment, Directorates of Tourism, Directorates of Rural Affairs, Directorates of Technical Projects
Democritus University of Thrace - Department of Civil Engineering, Department of Environmental Engineering
Eco Action
Ecological and Cultural Movement of Alonissos
Ecological Initiative of Chania
Ecological Intervention of Heraklion
Ecological Institute of Greece
Ecological Movement of Kavala
Ecological Movement of Patras
Ecological Movement of Thermaikos Gulf
Ecological School of Naxos
Ecological Society of Evros
Ecological Society of Recycling
ENALEIA
Environmental Organization of Zakynthos "Vrachionas"
Fishing Clubs / Associations
Fishing Vessel Owners' Association
Goulandris Natural History Museum / Greek Biotope Wetland Centre
Greek-Arab Chamber
Greek Center for the Care of Wild Animals and Birds
Greek-Italian Chamber
Greek-Romanian Chamber
Greek Wildlife Care Center (EKPAZ)
Greenpeace (Greece)
Group of Friends of Mountain-Sea
Hellenic Centre for Bird Ringing
Hellenic Center for Environment-Ecosystem Protection
Hellenic Coast Guard, Port Authorities
Hellenic Ecological Society (HELECOS)
Hellenic Federation for Underwater Activities & Sportfishing (E.O.Y.D.A)
Hellenic Institute for the Environment, Recycling and Conservation of Water Resources
Hellenic Scientific Society for Environmental Protection
Hellenic Society for Environmental Information and Education for

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Sustainability
Hellenic Society for the Protection of Nature, HSPN
Hellenic Zoological Society
HELMEPA, Hellenic Marine Environment Protection Association
Hotel Chamber of Greece
Institute of Fisheries Research - ELGO DIMITRA (INALE)
Institute of Natural Resources Management of Western Greece
International Hellenic University - Department of Civil Engineering
Ionian Environment Foundation
Ionian University - School of Environment
iSea, Environmental Organisation for the Preservation of the Aquatic Ecosystems
Magnesia Environmental Initiative
MedINA
Mediterranean SOS Network
Ministry of Environment and Energy (MoEE), Department of Environment, Special Office for the Coordination of Environmental Action (EYSPED)
Ministry of Environment and Energy (MoEE), General Secretariat for Energy & Mineral Resources, Directorate-General for Energy, Directorate for Hydrocarbons
Ministry of Environment and Energy (MoEE), General Secretariat for Energy & Mineral Resources, Directorate General for Energy, Directorate for Renewable Energy Sources and Alternative Fuels
Ministry of Environment and Energy (MoEE), General Secretariat of Natural Environment and Water, General Directorate of Environmental Policy, Directorate of Natural Environment and Biodiversity Management
Ministry of Environment and Energy (MoEE), General Secretariat of Natural Environment and Water, General Directorate of Water, Directorate of Planning and Management of Water Services
Ministry of Environment and Energy (MoEE), General Secretariat of Natural Environment and Water, General Directorate of Water, Directorate of Water Environment Protection and Management
Ministry of Maritime Affairs and Insular Policy
Ministry of Rural Development & Food, General Directorate for Fisheries
National and Kapodistrian University of Athens - Department of Biology, Department of Geology and Environment
National Technical University of Athens - Department of Civil Engineering
Natura DI ZANTE
Naturist Club of Fokidas Beach
Navy Chamber of Greece

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Naxos Ecological Research Center
Panhellenic Federation of Amateur Fishing Associations
Panhellenic Network of Ecological Organizations
Pelagos Cetacean Research Institute
Plastic Free Lesvos
Preveza Environmental Company
Protected Areas Management Units
Rhodes Island Environmental Protection Association
Samos Environment and Ecology Movement
Seafood and Aquaculture Associations
Society for the Environment and Cultural Heritage (ELLET)
Technical Chamber of Greece
Technological Educational Institution of Crete - Natural Resources and Environmental Engineering
The Green Tank
The Mediterranean Information Office for Environment, Culture and Sustainable Development, MIO-ECSDE
Thessaloniki Greek-Italian Chamber
Transdisciplinary Institute for Environmental and Social Studies, TIESS
Union of citizens of Thessaloniki for the environment and culture
Union of Hellenic Chambers
University of Patras - Department of Biology, Department of Environmental Engineering, Department of Civil Engineering
University of the Aegean - Department of Geography, Department of Environment
University of Thessaly - Department of Civil Engineering, Department of Ichthyology & Aquatic Environment
Veterinary Research Institute - ELGO DIMITRA
Wildlife and Bird Aid and Protection Station
Wildlife Protection and Care Center (KEPAZ)
WWF Hellas
Zakynthos Ecological Movement
ISRAEL
Ben-Gurion University of the Negev, Beersheba - Department of Earth and Environmental Sciences
Delphis Organization
EcoOcean
Israel Nature and Parks Authority
Israel Oceanographic & Limnological Research Institute
Ministry of Energy and Infrastructure
Ministry of Environmental Protection
Ministry of Transport and Road Safety, Administration of Shipping and

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Ports
Society for the Protection of Nature
University of Haifa, The Leon H. Charney School of Marine Sciences
ITALY
Biodiversity Protection Service
Cetacean Foundation - O.N.L.U.S. in Riccione
CIMA Research Foundation
Gargano National Park - Tremiti Islands - Puglia
Italian National Research Council, Institute for Marine Biological Resources and Biotechnology (CNR-IRBIM)
Italian National Research Council, Institute for the Study of Anthropic Impacts and Sustainability in Marine Environment (CNR-IAS)
Italian National Research Council, Institute of Marine Sciences CNR-ISMAR
Management Consortium of the Torre del Cerrano Marine Protected Area
MARETERRA ONLUS, Environmental research and conservation, Sardinia
Marine Protected Area Porto Cesareo
Ministry of Environment and Energy Security - Directorate General for Natural Heritage and the Sea
Ministry of Infrastructure and Transport
Miramare Marine Reserve
National Institute of Oceanography and Experimental Geophysics (Istituto Nazionale di Oceanografia e di Geofisica Sperimentale)
National Inter-University Consortium of Marine Sciences, a collaboration between 35 Italian Universities. CoNISMa
Puglia Region: Department of Environment, Landscape and Urban Quality
Sant Andrea Regional Natural Park and Punta Pizzon Coastline
Tethys Research Institute
University of Padova
Wildlife Center of the Province of Brindisi
JORDAN
Aqaba Diving Association
Ministry of Environment
Ministry of Transport, Jordan Maritime Authority
Royal Marine Conservation Society of Jordan (JREDS)
LEBANON
Ministry of Energy and Water
Ministry of Environment
Ministry of Public Works and Transport, Directorate General of Land and

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Maritime Transport
National Centre for Marine Sciences
Tyre Coast Nature Reserve
MONTENEGRO
Ministry of Ecology, Spatial Planning and Urbanism
Ministry of Transport and Maritime Affairs
PALESTINE
Environmental Quality Authority
Ministry of Environment
Ministry of Transportation
Palestinian Energy and Natural Resources Authority
Palestinian Water Authority
ROMANIA
Mare Nostrum NGO
Ministry of Environment, Waters and Forests
Ministry of Transport and Infrastructure
National Institute for Marine Research and Development "Grigore Antipa"
STATE of LIBYA
Ministry of Environment
Ministry of Livestock and Marine Resources
Ministry of Transportation
SYRIAN ARAB REPUBLIC
Ministry of Local Administration and Environment
Ministry of Water Resources
Ministry of Transport
Syrian Maritime Authority
Syrian Society for the Conservation of Wildlife (SSCW)
TUNISIA
Ministry of Environment
Ministry of Transport
National Agency for Coastal Protection
Specially Protected Areas Regional Activity Centre (SPA/RAC) Tunis
TURKEY
Central Fisheries Research Institute
Dokuz Eylul University - Institute of Marine Sciences and Technology
Istanbul University - Institute of Marine Sciences and Management, The Faculty of Aquatic Sciences
Marine Conservation Centre DEKAFOK
Marine Mammals Research Association (DMAD)
Middle East Technical University - Institute of Marine Sciences (IMS)
Ministry of Energy and Natural Resources

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Ministry of Environment, Urbanisation and Climate Change
Ministry of Transport and Infrastructure
Turkish Marine Environment Protection Association (TURMEPA)
Turkish Marine Research Foundation (TUDAV)
Tubitak Marmara Research Center
INTERNATIONAL NETWORKS AND ENTITIES
Adriatic Protected Areas Network (AdriaPAN)
Birdlife International
Black Sea Commission (BSC)
Black Sea NGO Network
Centre for Mediterranean Cooperation of the International Union for the Conservation of Nature (IUCN-Med)
Cetacean Alliance
EUROPARC Federation
European Marine Board
General Fisheries Commission for the Mediterranean (GFCM)
International Birdlife
International Council for the Exploration of the Sea (ICES)
International Science Council (ISC), Scientific Committee on Oceanic Research
International Whaling Commission (IWC)
Marine Conservation Research International (MCR)
Mediterranean Marine Protected Areas Network
Mediterranean Posidonia Network
Mediterranean Science Commission (CIESM)
OCEANA Europe
Regional Marine Pollution Emergency Response Centre for the Mediterranean Sea (REMPEC)
UNEP/CMS Agreement on the Conservation of Small Cetaceans of the Baltic
UNEP/MAP Mediterranean Action Plan (UNEP/MAP)
UNEP/MAP Specially Protected Areas Regional Activity Centre (UNEP/MAP/SPA-RAC)
WWF Mediterranean Programme Office

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Appendix II: Project areas of implementation, including Special Areas of Conservation (SACs) / Sites of Community Importance (SCIs) and Special Protection Areas (SPAs)

GREECE		
Code No	Name	N2K Status
GR1110013	Thalassia Periochi Thrakis	SAC/SCI
GR1150014	Thalassia Periochi Kavallas - Thasou	SAC/SCI - SPA
GR1430004	Ethniko Thalassio Parko Alonnisou - Voreion Sporadon, Anatoliki Skopelos	SAC/SCI
GR1430005	Nisia Kyra Panagia, Piperi, Psathoura Kai Gyro Nisides Agios Georgios, Nisoi Adelfoi, Lechousa, Gaidouronisia	SPA
GR2110001	Amvrakikos Kolpos, Delta Lourou Kai Arachthou (Petra, Mytikas, Evryteri Periochi, Kato Pous Arachthou, Kampi Filippiadas)	SAC/SCI
GR2210002	Kolpos Lagana Zakynthou (Akr. Geraki - Keri) Kai Nisides Marathonisi Kai Pelouzo	SAC/SCI
GR2210004	Nisides Stamfani Kai Arpyia (Strofades) Kai Thalassia Zoni	SPA
GR2220003	Esoteriko Archipelagos Ioniou (Meganisi, Arkoudi, Atokos, Vromonas)	SAC/SCI
GR2220007	Thalassia Zoni Apo Argostoli Eos Ormo Mounta	SAC/SCI
GR2230004	Nisoi Paxoi Kai Antipaxoi Kai Evryteri Thalassia Periochi	SAC/SCI
GR2230008	Diapontia Nisia (Othonoi, Ereikousa, Mathraki Kai Vrachonisides)	SPA
GR2310001	Delta Achelou, Limnothalassa Mesolongiou - Aitolikou, Ekvoles Evinou, Nisoi Echinades, Nisos Petalas	SAC/SCI
GR2330005	Thines Kai Paraliako Dasos Zacharos, Limni Kaiafa, Strofylia, Kakovatos	SAC/SCI
GR2330008	Thalassia Periochi Kolpou Kyparissias: Akr. Katakolo - Kyparissia	SAC/SCI
GR2420009	Nisides Skyrou Kai Thalassia Periochi	SPA
GR2420016	Thalassia Periochi Notiou Evvoikou Kolpou	SPA
GR2530007	Korinthiakos Kolpos	SAC/SCI
GR2540002	Periochi Neapolis Kai Nisos Elafonisos	SAC/SCI
GR2540003	Ekvoles Evrota, Periochi Vrontama Kai Thalassia Periochi Lakonikou Kolpou	SAC/SCI
GR2550005	Thines Kyparissias (Neochori - Kyparissia)	SAC/SCI
GR2550010	Thalassia Periochi Notias Messinias	SAC/SCI
GR3000012	Nisos Antikythira Kai Nisides Prasonisi,	SPA

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Project 101113792 - LIFE22-NAT-EL-LIFE MareNatura - LIFE-2022-SAP-NAT
Deliverable 4.1: Replicability and Transferability Plan (RTP)

	Lagouvardos, Plakoulithra Kai Nisides Thymonies	
GR3000019	Thalassia Periochi Kythiron	SPA
GR4210001	Kasos Kai Kasonisia - Evryteri Thalassia Periochi	SAC/SCI
GR4210003	Voreia Karpathos Kai Saria Kai Paraktia Thalassia Zoni	SAC/SCI - SPA
GR4210011	Vrachonisia Notiou Aigaiou: Velopoula, Falkonera, Ananes, Christiana, Pacheia, Fteno, Makra, Astakidonisia, Syrna - Gyro Nisia Kai Thalassia Zoni	SAC/SCI
GR4210021	Anatoliko Tmima Astypaleas Kai Nisides Kounoupi, Fteno, Chondropoulo, Koitsomytis, Moni, Agia Kyriaki, Tigani, Chondri, Ligno, Fokionisia, Katsagreli, Pontikoysa, Fidoysa, Ktenia Kai Thalassia Periochi	SPA
GR4210023	Nisides Karpathiou Pelagous: Megalo Sofrano, Sochas, Mikro Sofrano, Avgo, Divounia, Chamili, Astakidonisia	SPA
GR4210025	Anatoliko Tmima Nisou Symis Kai Nisides Kouloundros Seskli, Troumpeto, Marmaras, Karavalonisi, Megalonisi, Gialesino, Oxeia, Chondros, Platy, Nimos Kai Thalassia Periochi Nisou Symis	SPA
GR4210028	Nisos Kasos Kai Symplegma Kasonision Kai Thalassia Periochi	SPA
GR4220006	Nisos Polyaigos - Kimolos	SAC/SCI
GR4220021	Mikres Kyklades, Voreioanatoliki Amorgos, Anatolikes Aktes Donousas, Gyro Nisides Kai Thalassia Periochi	SPA
GR4220027	Nisides Mykonou: Rineia, Chtapodia, Kai Tragonisi Kai Thalassia Periochi	SPA
GR4220033	Nisos Gyaros Kai Thalassia Zoni	SCI - SPA
GR4310004	Dytika Asterousia (Apo Agiofarango Eos Kokkino Pyrgo)	SAC/SCI
GR4320006	Voreioanatoliko Akro Kritis: Dionysades, Elasa Kai Chersonisos Sidero (Akra Mavro Mouri - Vai - Akra Plakas) Kai Thalassia Zoni	SAC/SCI
GR4320011	Dionysades Nisoi Kai Thalassia Zoni	SPA
GR4330004	Prassano Farangi - Patsos - Sfakoryako Rema - Paralia Rethymnou Kai Ekvoli Geropotamou, Akr. Lianos Kavos - Perivolia	SAC/SCI
GR4340003	Chersonisos Rodopou - Paralia Maleme - Kolpos Chanion	SAC/SCI
GR4340013	Nisoi Gavdos Kai Gavdopoula	SAC/SCI
GR4340024	Thalassia Periochi Dytikis Kai Notiodytikis Kritis	SAC/SCI

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ITALY		
Code number	Name	N2K Status
IT9110040	Isole Tremiti	SPA
IT9120012	Scoglio dell' Eremita	SPA
IT9150015	Litorale di Gallipoli e Isola S. Andrea	SAC/SCI - SPA

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